

DrugProt submission step by step

antoniomiresc@gmail.com

IMPORTANT: This tutorial is for the DrugProt Main subtrack. Large-Scale predictions are done via FTP.

Steps:

1. Prepare **the ZIP file.**

You must submit **ONE SINGLE** ZIP file with the following structure:

- README.txt with contact details (registration team name, registration name and registration email) and a really short explanation of your system.
- A tab-separated file with your predictions.

If you have more than one system, name the tab-separated files with numbers and a more or less recognizable name. For example, 1-BERT.tsv and 2-dictionary-lookup.tsv.

Prediction file format. A tab-separated file with 4 columns: Document ID, relation type, first argument of the relation (a CHEMICAL) and second argument of the relation (a GENE).

Relation arguments are specified by their type (Arg1: or Arg2:) and their annotation mark (T1, T2, etc.)

Example TSV file:

12488248	INHIBITOR	Arg1:T2	Arg2:T52
23220562	ACTIVATOR	Arg1:T12	Arg2:T42

Example directory structure with the README and valid .tsv files

```
tutorial-ls-20210820T1315/  
├── 1-DeepLearning.tsv  
├── 2-dictionary-lookup.tsv  
├── 3-SVM.tsv  
├── 4-random.tsv  
├── 5-rules.tsv  
└── README.txt
```

2. Access <https://easychair.org/conferences/?conf=bc7>

3. Introduce your EasyChair **user name and password** (you may need to create a user, if you do not have one) and click Log In.

You should see the following page.

My EasyChair Help / Log out

Conferences CFP VCS Preprints Slides EasyChair

BC7 (BioCreative VII)

You are logged in to BC7 (BioCreative VII).
Use the links below to access BC7.

Author

- [make a new submission](#)

4. Click on **make a new submission**

5. Select **Track 1-DrugProt:Text mining drug/chemical-protein interactions**

BC7 (author) Help / Log out

New Submission BC7 Conference News EasyChair

Select a Track

Please select the track relevant for your submission and click "Continue".

- Track 1-DrugProt:Text mining drug/chemical-protein interactions
- Track 2-NLM-Chem Track: Full text Chemical Identification and Indexing in PubMed articles
- Track: * Track 3-Automatic extraction of medication names in tweets
- Track 4- COVID-19 text mining tool interactive demo
- Track 5- LitCovid track Multi-label topic classification for COVID-19 literature annotation

[Continue](#)

6. Fill in the **Author information**.

Author 1 ([click here to add yourself](#)) ([click here to add an associate](#))

First name†: * Antonio

Last name: * Miranda

Email: * antoniomiresc@gmail.com

Country/region: * Spain ▼

Organization: * Barcelona Supercomputing Center

Web page:

corresponding author

7. Fill in the **TITLE**. It **MUST** include your **registration team name**. If you do not remember your registration team name, email me at antoniomiresc@gmail.com

Title: * bsc-tutorial-predictions-v1

Abstract: *

Main Track predictions for BSC Tutorial test

For all submissions, you MUST use your registration name

8. Fill in the **keywords**.

Keywords: *

```
BSC Tutorial test team
predictions
main track
```

9. Upload the **ZIP** file and click **SUBMIT** (gz, tar and tgz files are also allowed).

Files

Submissions. Upload your Submission. For proceedings publications submit PDF format file. For other purposes follow instructions for your track. Note that the file size limit is 50 MB per submission.

Choose File No file chosen

Ready?

If you filled out the form, press the 'Submit' button below. **Do not press the button twice: uploading may take time!**

Submit

Congratulations! You have submitted your predictions. You should see a page like this:

The submission has been saved!

Submission 3	
Title:	bsc-tutorial-predictions-v1
Paper:	(Aug 27, 11:17 GMT)
Track:	Track 1-DrugProt: Text mining drug/chemical-protein interactions
Author keywords:	BSC Tutorial test team predictions main track
Abstract:	Main Track predictions for BSC Tutorial test
Submitted:	Aug 27, 11:17 GMT
Last update:	Aug 27, 11:17 GMT